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SUPER MoRRI – Scientific understanding and provision of an enhanced and robust monitoring system for RRI

D6.4 Testing, implementation, and training of the self-assessment tool

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1. Introduction and overview

1.1. Description of work and task

Task 6.4: Testing the self-assessment tool (SAT) and providing training for the tool (M18-M60;

Lead: TU Delft, supported by CSIC, IHS, AU, ULEI, SIMAVI ROMANIA)

- To test and implement self assessment dashboard within SUPER MoRRI partner organisations
- To test and implement self assessment dashboard within selected stakeholders as pilots

Milestone 9: Summary of implementation of the self-assessment tool (M60)

- By reaching M6.2, the project demonstrates the results of the tested, implemented and trained selfassessment tool. (M60)

Deliverable 6.4: Testing, implementation, and training of the self assessment tool (M60)

- D6.4 Testing, implementation, and training of the self assessment tool.

1.2. Work progress and achievements

- **Task 6.4: Testing the self-assessment tool and providing training for the tool (M18-M60);**
Lead: TU Delft, supported by CSIC, IHS, AU, ULEI, SIMAVI ROMANIA)
 - Achieved, see content of this deliverable
- **Milestone 6.1: Development of self-assessment tool (M48)**
 - We present in this report the structure and content of the SAT
- **Deliverable 6.3: Designing RRI assessment dashboard (M48)**
 - Submitted

1.3. Deliverable overview

No.	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Diss. Level	Due/Delivery date
D6.4	Testing, implementation, and training of the self assessment tool	TU Delft	Demonstrator	Public	M60

Table 1: Deliverable 6.4 overview

1.4. Deviations from the plan and problems encountered

There is no deviation from the plan.

2. OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE OF SELF-ASSESSMENT TOOL

2.1. Objective

The SUPER MoRRI Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) aims to provide a method of assistance to various types of stakeholder groups (primarily Research Performing Organizations (RPOs)) to measure/assess their performance in terms various RRI indicators. The SAT can be of use to Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) as well, but rather indirectly. Such tool can inform RFO policies in terms of defining indicators of interest that can be monitored and targets established at the level of funded projects.

The explicit aim of this tool (as highlighted in the SUPER MoRRI project proposal) is to allow RPOs to self-assess the current status of their implementation of RRI principles in running research and innovation projects, and monitor the development of this status over time.

2.2. User scope

User Role	Description
Project Manager	Manages all the information about the organization ¹ and project. This person is ultimately responsible for the information filled in the SAT about their project and organization. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Creates new projects in SAT;• Fills in general information about project and organization.• Can also input and view information about indicators.• Can see self-assessment reports about their projects.• Can add other users: Project Assistants, Project Workers.• Can access/view the SAT Dashboard
Project Assistant	Person appointed/added by the Project Manager to operate input data. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Fills in general information about project and organization.• Can also input and view information about indicators.• Can see self-assessment reports about their projects.• Can add other users: Project Workers.• Can access/view the SAT Dashboard
Project Worker	A project worker is any project worker that is added by the Project Manager or Project Assistant ; <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The project worker has viewing rights on information about the project.• Can access/view the SAT Dashboard;• If in the future some Self Assessment Information is asked in a survey format from project workers, the project workers will have input/editing access to such surveys.• Can access/view the SAT Dashboard

¹ For a future version of this document we may consider another user role "Organization representative" who manages the entire account for the respective organization and the projects that belong to it. For the moment, however, it does not make sense to make the user role list too complex.

User Role	Description
Unassociated user	User who has self-registered but has not (yet) been associated with a project and organization. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Can access/view the SAT Dashboard
Unregistered User	Any visitor of SAT on the Internet. <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Can access/view the SAT Dashboard

Table 2: User Roles

3. SELF ASSESSMENT TOOL IMPLEMENTATION

In this section we present the content of the tool based on the set of indicators (3.1) and the final digital online tool with screenshots (3.2).

3.1. Content: Indicators

Indicators are grouped in six categories, each with a number of sub-elements on a level-scale.

Category	Topics	Level	Actions
<p>C1. Stakeholder engagement in projects</p> <p>This topic concerns the ways and intensity with which colleagues/partners (internal stakeholders) and other representatives from societal groups / other companies (external stakeholders) are involved in research & development projects within your organisation.</p>	<p>Q1. Inclusion of internal stakeholders:</p> <p>This topic concerns the ways and intensity with which colleagues/partners (internal stakeholders) are involved in research & development projects within your organisation. This may range from limited information provision within the organisation, to full inclusion in decision making in a broad range of project-related activities.</p>	<p>Level 1 No engagement activities with internal stakeholders e.g. employees, researchers, etc.</p> <p>Level 2 Communication and consultation with internal stakeholders are limited, and their perspectives and expertise may not be fully considered.</p> <p>Level 3 Defined processes or guidelines for engagement of internal stakeholders. Efforts are made to involve internal stakeholders in relevant discussions or decision-making processes. However, the approach may still lack consistency or depth.</p> <p>Level 4 Internal stakeholder inclusion is integrated into the core practices and decision-making processes of the organization or project. There is open and transparent communication, and internal stakeholders feel empowered to contribute.</p> <p>Level 5 Internal stakeholders are viewed as critical partners and co-creators in shaping the organization's goals, strategies, and outcomes. Engagement with internal stakeholders is comprehensive, continuous, and proactive. There is a culture of inclusivity and collaboration, and internal stakeholders have meaningful influence and ownership over decision-making processes.</p>	<p>e.g., Identify the relevant internal stakeholders</p> <p>e.g., Have a plan for communication strategy with internal stakeholders</p> <p>e.g. Systematic approach to involve internal stakeholders at different stages</p> <p>e.g. Promote a culture of inclusivity and collaboration whenever possible</p>
	<p>Q2. Stakeholder inclusion in data collection and analysis</p> <p>The involvement of relevant stakeholders throughout the process of gathering and interpreting data. It recognizes that stakeholders, who have a vested interest or are affected by the research or project, can provide valuable insights, expertise, and perspectives that enrich the quality and relevance of data collection and analysis.</p>	<p>Level 1 No plans and ideas for stakeholder inclusion in data collection and analysis.</p> <p>Level 2 Sporadic, ad hoc, and not systematically stakeholder inclusion in data collection and analysis (with a limited awareness of the importance of stakeholder involvement)</p> <p>Level 3 Strategies for stakeholder inclusivity incl. gender diversity for data collection and analysis. Efforts are made to identify relevant stakeholders and incorporate their input. However, the approach may still lack consistency or depth.</p> <p>Level 4 Stakeholder inclusion is integrated into the core research or project processes. Plans for stakeholder contributions for data analysis / evaluation (including training strategies for stakeholders).</p> <p>Level 5 Stakeholder inclusion becomes a strategic priority and a transformative force. It goes beyond mere involvement and aims to empower stakeholders, promote equity, and address power imbalances.</p>	<p>e.g., identify the stakeholders who should be informed about the outcomes</p> <p>e.g., diversity of stakeholders in data collection and testing in terms of gender, age, experience</p> <p>e.g., inclusive plan for maintaining good stakeholder relations</p> <p>e.g., defined fair, transparent and planned processes</p>
	<p>Q3. Inclusion of external stakeholders:</p> <p>This concerns the ways in which representatives of other possibly affected stakeholder groups (users, societal groups, NGOs, policy makers, etc.) are included in project-related activities</p>	<p>Level 1 No consideration of identifying external stakeholders. Engagement with external stakeholders is limited, and their perspectives and needs may not be adequately considered. There is limited awareness of the importance of external stakeholder inclusion, and the organization or project lacks a systematic approach to engage them.</p> <p>Level 2 Recognizes the significance of external stakeholder inclusion and has established defined processes or guidelines for engagement. Efforts are made to identify and involve relevant stakeholders.</p> <p>Level 3 External stakeholder inclusion is integrated into the core practices and decision-making processes of the organization or project. Engagement with external stakeholders becomes a standard practice and is considered throughout the project lifecycle. Stakeholders are involved in key discussions, their perspectives are actively sought, and their input is incorporated into decision-making processes. Engagement mechanisms may include regular meetings, workshops, or collaborative platforms.</p> <p>Level 4 Developing strategies to accommodate relevant actors. External stakeholder inclusion becomes a strategic priority and a transformative force within the organization or project.</p> <p>Level 5 Fully active on external stakeholder involvement. Engagement is comprehensive and aims to empower stakeholders, address power imbalances, and promote equity. External stakeholders are involved in decision-making processes and have influence over project direction. There is an ongoing commitment to learning and adapting based on stakeholder feedback.</p>	<p>e.g., Look for a diversity of participants in terms of experience, geography, gender, and age</p> <p>e.g., Design stakeholder values hierarchy, conflicting values</p> <p>e.g., Develop strategies to accommodate all the relevant actors</p> <p>e.g., Have identified and specific processes for including all relevant stakeholders from the early stages of development</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">C2. Data Management</p> <p>Data management refers to the process of acquiring, organizing, storing, and maintaining data in a secure and efficient manner. It involves various activities and strategies to ensure data quality, accessibility, reliability, and security throughout its lifecycle. Key aspects of data management: Data collection, Data Integration, Data Storage, Data Governance, Data Security, Data Analysis, Data Lifecycle Management, Master Data Management (MDM), Data Documentation and Metadata Management</p>																
<p>Q1. Preparations for data collection in case of human subject research</p> <p>When conducting human subject research and preparing for data collection, it's important to follow ethical guidelines and ensure the privacy, confidentiality, diversity and inclusion, and well-being of the participants. How may this be organised?</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Level 1</td> <td>No explicit plan(s) for preparation of data collection in case of human subject research are considered</td> <td>e.g., simple data collection forms</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 2</td> <td>Has developed a Data collection plan but without prioritising the ethical aspects of research</td> <td>e.g., consent types of data and consider for who the data is available for</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 3</td> <td>Data collection plan with prioritising the ethical aspects of research and obtain the necessary approvals and permissions before conducting any data collection involving human subjects</td> <td>e.g., examine how to include underrepresented groups, define examples of sensitive data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 4</td> <td>Active procedures in place to consider diversity and inclusion in conducting any data collection involving human subjects</td> <td>e.g., Define sensitive staff, consider political viewpoints, sexual orientation and define degrees of sensitivity data</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 5</td> <td>Fully inclusive and ethical plans for conducting any data collection involving human subjects</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Level 1	No explicit plan(s) for preparation of data collection in case of human subject research are considered	e.g., simple data collection forms	Level 2	Has developed a Data collection plan but without prioritising the ethical aspects of research	e.g., consent types of data and consider for who the data is available for	Level 3	Data collection plan with prioritising the ethical aspects of research and obtain the necessary approvals and permissions before conducting any data collection involving human subjects	e.g., examine how to include underrepresented groups, define examples of sensitive data	Level 4	Active procedures in place to consider diversity and inclusion in conducting any data collection involving human subjects	e.g., Define sensitive staff, consider political viewpoints, sexual orientation and define degrees of sensitivity data	Level 5	Fully inclusive and ethical plans for conducting any data collection involving human subjects	
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<p>Q2. Data collection & analysis methods</p> <p>The processes and techniques use to gather and examine data in order to extract meaningful insights and make informed decisions. For Data collection this refers to involving systematically gathering relevant data from various sources, which can include surveys, interviews, observations, experiments, existing databases, and more. Data analysis methods are employed to transform the raw data into meaningful information</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Level 1</td> <td>No explicit plan for systematically gathering relevant data from various sources, as well as transform the raw data into meaningful information</td> <td>e.g., transparent presentation to involved actors</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 2</td> <td>Scanning data collection and data analysis requirements incl. data gathering incl. GDPR compliance and sensitivity of data analysis</td> <td>e.g., transparent presentation to involved actors</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 3</td> <td>Presenting data and outcomes transparently by e.g. providing context, using clear visuals, explaining data sources and collection methods, sharing assumptions and limitations</td> <td>e.g., identify the goals and expected outcomes to all stakeholders in advance</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 4</td> <td>Co-designed plan with stakeholders for data collection and data analysis</td> <td>e.g., identify and communicate the goals and expected outcomes to all stakeholders in advance</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 5</td> <td>Explicit, transparent, and fully engaged with stakeholders for data collection and data analysis</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Level 1	No explicit plan for systematically gathering relevant data from various sources, as well as transform the raw data into meaningful information	e.g., transparent presentation to involved actors	Level 2	Scanning data collection and data analysis requirements incl. data gathering incl. GDPR compliance and sensitivity of data analysis	e.g., transparent presentation to involved actors	Level 3	Presenting data and outcomes transparently by e.g. providing context, using clear visuals, explaining data sources and collection methods, sharing assumptions and limitations	e.g., identify the goals and expected outcomes to all stakeholders in advance	Level 4	Co-designed plan with stakeholders for data collection and data analysis	e.g., identify and communicate the goals and expected outcomes to all stakeholders in advance	Level 5	Explicit, transparent, and fully engaged with stakeholders for data collection and data analysis	
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<p>Q3. Data output and delivering results</p> <p>Preparing and delivering the results of data analysis to stakeholders in a meaningful and accessible format. It focuses on transforming the analyzed data into clear and actionable insights that can inform decision-making.</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Level 1</td> <td>No explicit plan for delivering data analysis results to stakeholders</td> <td>e.g., Initial risk assessment and taking into account diversity</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 2</td> <td>Risks of confidentiality breaches of data outputs and robust security measures considered</td> <td>e.g., Partnership co-publications and other communication channels</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 3</td> <td>Classification of data outputs considering different type of data, i.e. Structured vs. Unstructured Data - Quantitative vs. Qualitative Data - Aggregated vs. Individual Data - Internal vs. External Data - Public vs. Confidential Data - Research vs. Operational Data</td> <td>e.g., Analyses the relevancy of outcomes for other purposes and practitioners</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 4</td> <td>Effectively manage, analyze, interpret, and utilize the classified data outputs to different audiences and to derive meaningful insights, drive decision-making, and achieve desired outcomes in research or operational contexts</td> <td>e.g., GDPR compliance, anonymity and confidentiality</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 5</td> <td>Responsible data maintenance and storage tools are actively used or/and (re)developed within the (project) organization and corporate management</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Level 1	No explicit plan for delivering data analysis results to stakeholders	e.g., Initial risk assessment and taking into account diversity	Level 2	Risks of confidentiality breaches of data outputs and robust security measures considered	e.g., Partnership co-publications and other communication channels	Level 3	Classification of data outputs considering different type of data , i.e. Structured vs. Unstructured Data - Quantitative vs. Qualitative Data - Aggregated vs. Individual Data - Internal vs. External Data - Public vs. Confidential Data - Research vs. Operational Data	e.g., Analyses the relevancy of outcomes for other purposes and practitioners	Level 4	Effectively manage, analyze, interpret, and utilize the classified data outputs to different audiences and to derive meaningful insights, drive decision-making, and achieve desired outcomes in research or operational contexts	e.g., GDPR compliance, anonymity and confidentiality	Level 5	Responsible data maintenance and storage tools are actively used or/and (re)developed within the (project) organization and corporate management	
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<p>Q4. Open access and Transparency</p> <p>refers to the practice of providing unrestricted and free access to research data</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Level 1</td> <td>No explicit plan for open access in data management</td> <td>e.g., Provide clear and open licenses</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 2</td> <td>Minimum steps taken to support open access to data management e.g. use open data formats, provide clear and open licenses, publish data in open repositories, include metadata and documentation, practice data anonymization and privacy protection, share data through APIs</td> <td>e.g., Organize public dialogues</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 3</td> <td>Implement data management plans to engage in open data collaborations and educate and raise awareness among internal and external stakeholders about open access in data management</td> <td>e.g., Use public platforms for expressing needs and concerns</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 4</td> <td>Data structure with clear plan for establish data sharing agreements, foster a culture of data sharing, support data curation and preservation, conduct data sharing and reuse studies, and collaborate with data repositories and platforms</td> <td>e.g., Organize social experimentation using participatory methods</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Level 5</td> <td>Fully inclusive plan for open access incl. encouraging data citation and attribution, participating in data quality assurance, fostering data interoperability, engaging with the open science community, monitoring and evaluate data impact, and contributing to data infrastructure development</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Level 1	No explicit plan for open access in data management	e.g., Provide clear and open licenses	Level 2	Minimum steps taken to support open access to data management e.g. use open data formats, provide clear and open licenses, publish data in open repositories, include metadata and documentation, practice data anonymization and privacy protection, share data through APIs	e.g., Organize public dialogues	Level 3	Implement data management plans to engage in open data collaborations and educate and raise awareness among internal and external stakeholders about open access in data management	e.g., Use public platforms for expressing needs and concerns	Level 4	Data structure with clear plan for establish data sharing agreements, foster a culture of data sharing, support data curation and preservation, conduct data sharing and reuse studies, and collaborate with data repositories and platforms	e.g., Organize social experimentation using participatory methods	Level 5	Fully inclusive plan for open access incl. encouraging data citation and attribution, participating in data quality assurance, fostering data interoperability, engaging with the open science community, monitoring and evaluate data impact, and contributing to data infrastructure development	
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<p style="text-align: center;">C3. Internal organisational management & governance</p> <p style="text-align: center;">This topic concerns the integration of Responsible Research & Innovation actions in corporate (organization) management strategies</p>	<p>Q1. RRI strategies in internal management operations</p> <p>This topic includes the organization of (internal/external) input on internal decision making processes on organizational structures / governance, including e.g. the distribution of tasks amongst departments,</p>	<p>Level 1 No consideration of having RRI impact strategies in management</p> <p>Level 2 RRI and impact strategies are taken into consideration, e.g. through socially responsible entrepreneurship programs</p> <p>Level 3 Impact strategies present and visible through e.g. employees dedicated to socially responsible product/service/conduct development, and management structures explicitly for RRI in project governance</p> <p>Level 4 Evaluation of organisation's impacts and RRI efforts, e.g. through reporting of responsible-conduct-relevant choices in communications, and formal trainings about RRI/ethics to staff</p> <p>Level 5 Financial, non-financial and RRI components are connected and present in the formal organisational structure. e.g. through (significant) percentage of RRI-relevant expenditures vis-a-vis profit.</p>	<p>e.g., Consideration of Socially Responsible Innovation/Entrepreneurship strategies</p> <p>e.g., installing ethics / responsible conduct advisory board and having dedicated responsible entrepreneurship tasks within the organization</p> <p>e.g., Evaluation and monitoring strategies for RRI, or, (externally organised) responsibility-relevant trainings for staff</p> <p>e.g., Qualitative and quantitative assessment of societal impacts</p>
	<p>Q2. RRI strategies in external management operations</p> <p>This topic includes the organization of (external, multi-stakeholder) input on decision making processes on organizational structures / governance, including e.g. the development of social trust of the organization and responsible business conduct</p>	<p>Level 1 No consideration of external input on organizational governance</p> <p>Level 2 Plans to develop capacity and mechanisms for appraisal and foresight/anticipation of organizational output (e.g. science/technology/knowledge/innovation), also to prevent unintended use or misuse of outcomes</p> <p>Level 3 Explicit plans for integrating public and societal values in strategic future plans, e.g. through dialogues and deliberation with external parties</p> <p>Level 4 Initiatives that promote and reassure active external stakeholder engagement and responsible governance</p> <p>Level 5 Specific and explicit ways of communicating social norms and responsible business conduct.</p>	<p>e.g., dual use technology investigations and other consequence investigation and anticipation studies</p> <p>e.g., dialogue plans to include societal actors (stakeholder groups, investors, suppliers, share holders) in future strategic planning</p> <p>e.g., wide array of activities to involve external stakeholder groups in future strategy planning sessions</p> <p>e.g., co-designing future business plans with involved stakeholders, through inclusive design methods</p>
	<p>Q3. RRI strategies in organizational innovation operations (internal development)</p> <p>This topic includes RRI actions on future product/service portfolio development and associated strategic choices for the future of the (market position of) the organization</p>	<p>Level 1 No consideration of having RRI in future product/service planning. Just legal compliance in projects and basic risk analysis.</p> <p>Level 2 Plans exist for developing a more socially/ethically sensitive future project portfolio, e.g. also through inclusion of responsible conduct in mission/vision, beyond legal compliance</p> <p>Level 3 Explicit consideration of social needs and e.g. sustainable development goals (SDGs) in future project planning (with explicit growth perspective on social responsible conduct)</p> <p>Level 4 Co-developed (with external stakeholders) plans for future projects, safeguarding public/societal values in innovation strategy. Risk analysis of future projects includes social/ethical dimensions.</p> <p>Level 5 Significant share of socially/ethically oriented projects with active external stakeholder involvement.</p>	<p>e.g., develop socially responsible mission/vision to help guide the organisations future project portfolio</p> <p>e.g., consider EU sustainable development goals explicitly in novel project ideas/applications/initiations</p> <p>e.g., responsibly co-develop future project ideas with external stakeholders, through e.g. Living Labs or other participatory methods</p> <p>e.g., available structures, methods and expertise to safeguard stakeholder involvement in future project planning</p>

<p>C4. (Gender) diversity in organizational governance</p> <p>This topic concerns the explicit consideration and implementation of (gender) diversity and distribution within the organization of project management, including doing this within the execution of projects.</p>	<p>Q1. (Gender) distribution in projects:</p> <p>This concerns the implementation of gender diversity policies within current and future projects</p> <p>Q2. Corporate management in project driven organizations</p> <p>This concerns specific (gender) sensitivity within the corporate management structures, including equality in e.g. pay-gap, career opportunities and recruitment processes</p>	<p>Level 1 No gender diversity considered in project management/ governance</p> <p>Level 2 Recognition of the importance of having a gender distribution policy in projects</p> <p>Level 3 Identification of main diversity related aspects that play a role in projects (including gender, experience, age, etc.), and consideration thereof in e.g. balance in groups of inventors / initiators</p> <p>Level 4 Active procedures to ensure (gender) equality within projects, and means to mitigate risks of possible discrimination against (underrepresented) groups, including e.g. training initiatives within the project.</p> <p>Level 5 No discriminations and active policy enforcement for running and novel projects</p> <p>Level 1 No explicit diversity issues considered on corporate management level</p> <p>Level 2 The organisation has developed a plan for diversity / inclusion and gender balance in project teams and management.</p> <p>Level 3 Has identified strategies for equal career opportunities, no pay-gap between genders and gender-balanced recruitment committees and procedures.</p> <p>Level 4 Active procedures to tackle (gender) equality in organizational management, and development of trainings for sensitivity of related aspects to staff</p> <p>Level 5 Fully inclusive procedures and risk mitigation practices for (gender) inequalities within the projects and corporate management</p>	<p>e.g., develop a framework for having a gender distribution policy in projects</p> <p>e.g., Identification of the main diversity aspects (gender, experience, age) that projects may need in their execution</p> <p>e.g., Active procedures to ensure gender equality in all innovative projects and to tackle any possible discrimination in project planning (against (gender) diversity, advancement of women or other possibly underrepresented groups)</p> <p>e.g., active management and constant awareness of gender distribution and equality, such as diversity & inclusion bodies within projects</p> <p>e.g. awareness and ambition to develop plans of gender / diversity elements including pay-gaps, equal career opportunities and recruitment processes.</p> <p>e.g. developing extensive plans of gender / diversity elements including pay-gaps, equal career opportunities and recruitment processes.</p> <p>e.g., Establish an ethical, social, and legal monitoring board to maintain input and critical appraisal of gender / inclusion / diversity actions</p> <p>e.g., Inclusive procedures addressed and enforced at a corporate management level</p>
<p>C5. Ethics</p> <p>Consideration of ethics in projects is reflected in part through the other topics in this self-assessment. Still, some elements may be taken into consideration separately, including integrity and compliance regulations, ethics committees and some others that are described below.</p>	<p>Q3. Ethics</p>	<p>Level 1 No consideration of ethics, absence of ethics plans, or other plans taking into account social, environmental or health impacts</p> <p>Level 2 Consideration of developing ethical plans or guidelines, such as (gender) diversity plans, integrity & compliance regulations or (independent) ethics committees / review boards to assess (research) operations</p> <p>Level 3 Having ethical plans, but without explicitly being aware of these, or enforcing such plans</p> <p>Level 4 Having and enforcing plans, and also exploration and reflection of newly emerging possible ethical/moral impacts or problems that may emerge</p> <p>Level 5 Ethics assessment and evaluation and forecasting tools are actively used and (re)developed within the (project)organization</p>	<p>e.g., set specific targets in R&I strategies in order to provide solutions for sustainable development goals, Include RRI principles in company's mission and vision, include reflection on creating shared value</p> <p>e.g., develop and introduce ethical frameworks, codes of conduct, installing review boards, hiring compliance officers, etc.</p> <p>e.g., solicit ethical, social, environmental, health-related advice from (independent and external) experts</p> <p>e.g., Conduct ethical analysis and ethics impact assessment through foresight, scenario analysis, social phenomena, trends evaluation, etc.</p>

C6. Science Education & Communication	
<p>This topic considers activities that can be deployed to inform other stakeholders, outside of the project team, about the possibly relevant outcomes of the project. It includes three main platforms for this: outcomes relevant for educational purposes, for public actor groups, and for other professionals.</p>	<p>Q1. (Public) education initiatives</p> <p>Knowledge developed within the project may benefit other societal actor groups. How may this be organised?</p> <p>Level 1 Educational activities for other actors than those present in the project team, are not considered. e.g., consider reaching other stakeholder groups through social media activities</p> <p>Level 2 Project team is considering education / training activities for other actors, but there is no specific plan yet. e.g., Identify the possibly benefited actors groups, such as local schools, students, interest groups, etc.</p> <p>Level 3 Project team has plans for identifying and training others, outside the project team / organization e.g., Organise science cafes or public lectures as an opportunity to present in the public domain</p> <p>Level 4 Team has developed educational activities for others and has attuned these activities to the explicit needs and desires of these stakeholders e.g., develop and include activities for specific stakeholder groups like community schools and actor groups</p> <p>Level 5 Fully inclusive and country / actor group specific educational activities have been developed.</p>
	<p>Q2. Public impact and communication</p> <p>Project outcomes may be of public interest or contribute to public understanding of science. How can this be stimulated?</p> <p>Level 1 This project will not have any outcomes or implications that are or will be of general public interest e.g., Consider how results / outcomes may be of public interest</p> <p>Level 2 Outcomes are identified that may have implications for public actors, who are worth being informed about such relevant outcomes. e.g., Identify and assess the project's public impact with questionnaires, queries</p> <p>Level 3 Explicit efforts for Identification and assessment of projects' public impact, and active identification of possibly interested actors e.g., Give all participants the opportunity to learn about project outputs</p> <p>Level 4 Results are made available to a diverse set of identified stakeholders that have a use for the outcomes of the project e.g., explore stakeholder concerns, expectations, and perceptions related to project outcomes</p> <p>Level 5 Public events and other channels are explicitly used too spread project results to specific audiences</p>
	<p>Q3. Professional relevance</p> <p>Other professionals might have a use for the methods and outcomes of this project. How to share relevant insights with the professional peer-community?</p> <p>Level 1 Professional relevance of the project for others is not considered e.g., assessing relevance of used theoretical framework for others</p> <p>Level 2 Consideration of project outcome relevance for others, but no specific plan for sharing methods and insights e.g. developing ideas for publication of methodological papers for peer-community</p> <p>Level 3 Identification and assessment of professional relevance and suitable sharing platforms such as papers, conferences, reports e.g., promote the new methods and techniques to other researchers through publications</p> <p>Level 4 Making available used methods, techniques and outcomes to other researchers e.g., interdisciplinary involvement in processes and project activities, also before they have direct outcomes</p> <p>Level 5 Adoption of interdisciplinary research/development approaches</p>

3.2. Online user-interface (screenshots of SAT)

The online tool can be accessed via the tool-pilot webpage: <http://195.82.130.213/login>

Figure 1: Login screen

Figure 2: SAT entry portal, displaying which projects a user is engaged in

Figure 3: Project dashboard, displaying performance indicators and progress scores in time

Figure 4: Data entry portal, within which users can enter their scores to the indicators.

4. TESTING AND TRAINING: PILOT STUDY

On September 26th 2023, a pilot study was carried out within which the international satellite partners (ISPs) and prospective users of the tool were invited to reflect on the functionality of the tool. The results presented in Section 3 of this report, include adjustments made based on these insights.

We hosted an online workshop session with a total of 12 participants, for two hours, in which our tool development partner (SIMAVI) was present, as well as the ISP coordinator (UPF Barcelona) and the SAT content developer team (TU Delft). The recommendations of the ISP and professionals that were distilled during this session, are noted below.

4.1. Recommendations for tool development

Below we list the recommendations of our pilot users. This led to tweaks in the SAT, but not all elements have been included: some were not feasible to include within the timeframe of the project, or not required for a functional pilot. We acknowledge that always more and better functionalities may be developed, but had to restrict ourselves to the development of a functional tool that provides basic benchmarking options as identified as objectives of this project.

'Save' button

- One per subpage
- Make the button 'responsive', confirming it saved, in a nice way (no extra clicking)
- ACTION SIMAVI

Category description

- The overall category description is not presented, e.g. what is 'Internal organisational management & governance'. There is a short description of the categories in Miro that is not present in the tool. I don't mean the description around questions themselves, they are visible, but the overarching categories.
- ACTION SIMAVI

Numbers and sizes in the donut graph

- Users acknowledge that the size of the parts of the donut are not per se intuitive, and the numbers are not understood. Consider alternatively, to not display the numbers, just the relative size (without numbers) and colors, but then we should also add a 'legend'
- When I click on the pie chart, i navigate to the questions...when I click on the %age, the whole thing goes to 0.0...this is confusing
- On project score landing page, it's not immediately clear what's being displayed. One figures it out eventually that one is looking at the responses to the "exploded" segment of the circle chart...but it takes a minute. Perhaps something above the horizontal bar chart itself?
- ACTION TUD: make a legend description
- ACTION SIMAVI: remove numbers, add legend

Visual graph 'in time'

- Visuals in the bottom right graph: different visualization, not the overlapping triangles

- Only display 100% scores
- ACTION SIMAVI

Item descriptions

- Sentences confusing for people who are not familiar with Jargon: look at the texts.
- At points too difficult
- Wording is sometimes very complicated, sometimes the separation is somewhat arbitrary. Wording needs development.
- Content of levels is ambiguous in some cases; e.g., in Gender --- the difference between Active procedures; inclusive procedures; and fully inclusive procedures
- Content wording is difficult to understand in several cases (e.g., often a bit more complicated / complex. Could be clearer.)
- ACTION TUD: make easier

Entering data

- Make sure that surveys are 100% completed / give 'error' when not complete?

Bar charts top left

- also, worth adding horizontal indicators between 0 and 5 for the bar charts

Bigger picture website / instructions page

- List of topics somewhere, what is included in which section, to better understand the broader picture.
- Overall instructions page
- Be clear about timing within project: how to incorporate
- ACTION TUD: make instructions page

Extra comments section

- Add the option, per entered survey, to also have a qualitative data field (comments/remarks field)
- Add the option to add 'defence' or rationale for certain scores. Per topic, or in general?
- Also a 'free writing section' also you can collect views and ideas.
- ACTION SIMAVI: develop the option to enter comments per survey.
- ACTION TUD: think about when and where to display this info

Compare outcomes between people who fill in the survey

- Compare respondents' answers would be beneficial, in one graph, not in a report view.
- Can we develop something, like that there are 'bar charts' for a given timeframe (e.g. all surveys entered in the last week), and then if you click the 'items' on the top left horizontal bar chart, it will give the survey results of that particular item, not just the final outcomes of the whole survey
- ACTION SIMAVI: develop this function

How far are you in the survey?

- Can we add a dynamic display, that says: you have now answered 'X out of Y questions'
- ACTION SIMAVI: make this function

To consider

- Develop a simpler 'light' version of the tool
- HTTPS should be built in (for some organizations, this may be firewalled)
- Perhaps start with a simpler version, difficult to understand the difference between the items, in particular for non-native speakers, to understand the difference between options. Perhaps a simpler version first?
- Add other languages
- Add the possibility to highlight at what 'stage' your project is (starting up, data gathering, analysis, reporting?)
- The texts of the recommendations: that is not so helpful for who has already had a lower score, so also refer to a further resource, a citation, an advise, a 'tag' to the rest of the Dashboard/platform.
- Concepts are complicated, so perhaps 'hover-over' definitions and descriptions.
- the two-column layout for the topic and the question prompt/then the multiple choice list is a bit visually confusing to me -- like I don't know where to look first. (versus just straight down the page with more visual distinction)
- if there's only one contribution to ethics and 4 to another, is that a balanced scoring mechanism?
- No way to navigate easily back to the "my project page" from the scorecard?
- Regarding recommendations, it could be helpful to point not only to general statements like "design stakeholder values hierarchy" directly to a web resource or a method...the accompanying user manual, even

Use cases?

- Adding different perspectives: management does 360 evaluations where everyone has a voice, help make clearer how things are done.
- How does the tool gets used in practice: If there's no opportunity to provide external evidence, there is no way for people to validate the claim, then it remains empty. Chain of accountability. Notes to be added?
- I would only use it if funding bodies would require it, or if management says you have to use it.
- Portfolio of a bunch of projects as a funding organization, then deploy this as a survey tool? Or could be used as an evaluation tool for whole portfolio of program (a la the tender from DG RTD on evaluation of Horizon Europe...as a survey...)
- and likely only if required by the organizations owning the projects or the funding.

Report

- Single questions come out on different lines in the report. Bar charts for items within the categories

5. FUTURE OUTLOOK

The SUPER MoRRI Self-Assessment Tool (SAT) aims to provide a method of assistance to various types of stakeholder groups (primarily Research Performing Organizations (RPOs)) to measure/assess their performance in terms various RRI indicators. We acknowledge that a Self-Assessment Tool for RPOs may have additional functionalities, in addition to the basic functionalities that what we have built into the tool at this moment. We hope that follow-up projects will be further inspired by the current version and content of the tool to help RPOs to self-assess their project in light of RRI indicators.

SUPER MoRRI

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